

PHTHALONITRILE POLYMER FOAM FOR HIGH TEMPERATURE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the development of light weight foams based on phthalonitrile thermoset resin for high temperature applications. An effective foaming method was established through synchronizing the polymer viscosity profile and the thermal decomposition of chemical blowing agent. The effects of various foaming parameters, including the viscosity, foaming agents, and temperature on the foaming were discussed. Rigid closed-cell foams with density as low as 0.08 g/cm³ were obtained and can be used at temperature up to 300 °C. The thermal properties obtained from the foams were unattainable by other reported thermoset foams.

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing interest in replacing traditional metal foams with polymeric foams generated a great drive in the development of rigid polymeric foams for high temperature (HT) applications. This new material takes the advantage of the thermal stability, chemical resistance while maintaining the low density. Other excellent characteristic such as superior acoustic, strength-to-weight ratio, cost effectiveness and ease of being processed in various forms make polymeric foams increasingly attractive. The stringent requirements, however, have eliminated majority of the polymeric candidates due to the low service temperature. So far only few reported HT polymer foams and often with shortcomings. For instance, foaming of polybenzimidazoles (PBI) required temperatures above 400 °C [1], rigid polyimide (PI) foam developed by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration required tedious fabrication procedures [2]. Foams made from epoxy, polyurea, polypyrrones, and phenolic resins were also developed, however still with limited service temperature [3-6].

An appropriate matrix is crucial to meet HT requirements. Phthalonitrile-based polymers have been identified by various reports of possessing excellent thermal stability that matches or even surpasses that of PBI or PI. [7-15], however, mostly with processing temperature more than 200 °C. Much attention was paid on the development of new phthalonitrile based void free polymer and its composites or copolymer with long pot life. Phthalonitrile based foam was never reported. The thermoset nature precluded most of the possible foaming methods and the high operating temperature posed even more challenge to the task. To the contrary of the past researches, this new area requires short processing time and low processing temperature to facilitate the selection of blowing agents and to ensure proper foaming process. This paper presents the development of PN based foams through establishing a well synchronized system between PN crosslinking and chemical blowing agent (CBA) thermal decomposition. Resorcinol based phthalonitrile (PN) resin was chosen for the study for its relatively lower melting point.

2. EXPERIEMNTALS

Materials

Materials synthesis: Resorcinol, 4-nitrophthalonitrile, anhydrous potassium carbonate, anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used as received. PN was prepared following a modified procedure described by Keller et al [16]. Resorcinol, 4-nitrophthalonitrile and pulverized anhydrous potassium carbonate, at molar ratio of 1:2:3 were added into a 150 ml, three-neck round bottom flask equipped with magnetic stirring device. The mixture was stirred for 24 hrs in inert environment at room temperature in DMSO before poured slowly into dilute hydrochloric acid solution. The obtained pale yellow precipitate i.e. was filtered by vacuum-assisted filtration and washed with deionized water.

Prepolymer preparation: Prepolymer was prepared by adding 1, 4-bis (4-aminophenoxy) benzene (APB), purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry and used as received, to the molten PN monomer in round bottom flask with N₂ purge. The mixture was quenched after 10 to 15 minutes of stirring.

Prepolymer viscosity: the viscosity of PN prepolymer melt was obtained using Anton Paar Physica MCR501 equipped with precision heat control chamber. Cone and plate set up was used. The viscosity was obtained as a function of temperature at steady shear rate of 1/s.

Chemical blowing agent characterization

Gas liberation number: 1 g of CBA was sealed in glass container and immersed in pre-heated silicone oil bath. Gas liberated due to thermal decomposition under isothermal heating was collected and measured using measuring cylinder. The gas volume was recorded as the amount of gas liberated from 1 g of CBA at a fixed temperature, unit, cm³/g.

Thermal decomposition: Thermal decomposition of the CBA was studied using a TA Instruments Thermogravimetric Analyzer Q500. Dynamic heating at 190, 200, 210 and 220 °C at heating rate of 10 min⁻¹ and isothermal heating at 220 °C were performed in flowing nitrogen or air (40 ml/min).

The amount of CBA to be used:

$$\text{Gas liberated} = \text{Mold volume} - M_p/\rho_p \quad (1)$$

$$\text{CBA amount} = \text{Gas liberated} / (\text{Gas liberation number/g}) \quad (2)$$

M_p and ρ_p are the mass and density of the foam in the mold respectively.

Foaming process

PN foams were developed by a one-step foaming process as illustrated by Figure 1. CBA was mixed with the prepolymer and sealed in aluminium mold and heated in oven at 220 C for 2 hrs for foam formation. The foamed samples were demolded and postcured at 250-2 hrs and 280-2 hrs, 350-6hrs and 375-6 hrs.

Figure 1: Diagram illustrating the one-step foaming process.

Foam Characterizations

Morphology: The porous structure was examined using a JEOL 6360 scanning electron microscope (SEM). Cross sections of the rigid foam were fractured perpendicular to the foaming direction, sputter coated with gold before morphology observation.

Thermal properties: Thermal properties were studied using TGA Q500, TA Instruments. Dynamic heating from 50 to 850°C at heating rate of 10 °C/min was performed in flowing nitrogen or air at flow rate of 40 ml/min.

Foam Density (ρ_f):

$$\text{Density} = \text{mass} / \text{volume} \quad (3)$$

Average cell diameter (D): The average cell diameter is larger than the circular segment observed from scanning electron microscope (SEM), because the cells are randomly truncated at the plane of the specimen fracture surface. D was determined according to Equation 4, by assuming that the foam consists of randomly distributed cells.

$$D = d/(\pi/4) \quad (4)$$

d is the measured diameter in the micrographs obtained by SEM, 150 – 200 cells were used to obtain average D.

Bubble nucleation number/Cell density (N_o): the number of bubbles nucleated per cubic centimetre of the foams is given by:

$$N_o = N_f/(1-V_f) \quad (5)$$

where V_f is the void fraction and can be estimated by:

$$V_f = 1 - \rho_f/\rho \quad (6)$$

The bubble count obtained from SEM micrograph is used to calculate N_f :

$$N_f = (nM^2/A)^{3/2} \quad (7)$$

where n is the number of bubbles in the micrograph, A is the area of the micrograph, and M is the magnification factor.

Foaming grade (F_G) is determined by the foam density:

$$F_g = (1-\rho_f)/\rho_p \cdot 100\% \quad (8)$$

ρ_f and ρ_p are densities of the foam and bulk polymer respectively.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Foaming Condition Determination

A balance between viscosity and gas evolution is necessary to obtain stable foam with the highest possible foam volume. This is particularly important in thermoset systems which involve simultaneous polymerization of the liquid component and gas liberation from CBA. For a system with rapid viscosity increase from fast polymerization, the gas evolution may cease before the desired foam volume is reached, especially for low-density foams. On the other hand, if the increase in viscosity is too slow, foam stabilization may take longer time than desired and result in foam collapse. An ideal foaming system consists of a polymer with gelation time that coincides with the time when rapid gas liberation occurs; hence the solidifying polymer will be able to ‘trap’ the gas bubbles inside the matrix.

CBA thermal decomposition thermograph and the viscosity profile of PN prepolymer melt at different temperature were correlated to obtain a balanced system for proper foam fabrication.

Figure 2a shows the amount of gas liberated from CBA is temperature dependant. Below 200 °C, incomplete degradation of CBA liberated insufficient amount of gas to be dissolved in the polymer melt. This reduced the gas concentration in the polymer melt and hindered bubble formation. Lower gas concentration also slowed down bubble growth because of the small pressure difference. As clearly shown in Figure 2b, CBA decomposed at a relatively narrow time frame at 220 °C, it is crucial to obtain a PN system which gels within the time frame in order to match the rapid gas liberation rate. In this study, we define gelation as the state when drastic viscosity increase was observed from the viscosity versus time graph. The gain in melt strength through crosslinking was crucial in providing resistance to prevent the cellular structures from collapse, hence stabilize the bubbles before gas liberation ceases. To the contrary of all the past research which focused on the development of phthalonitrile based polymer with long pot life, a fast gelling system need to be developed in this case.

The gelation time was successfully reduced to within 10 minutes through proper additive selection, temperature adjustment, and prepolymer preparation. 1, 4-bis-aminophenoxy (APB) was found to be the most appropriate additive. Figure 3 shows the viscosity profiles obtained for PN/APB at different temperature under steady shear rate of 1/s. Results from Figure 2a and Figure 3 were overlaid and presented in Figure 4. At 190 °C, no gelation was observed after 20 min of heating, and CBA liberated limited amount of gas for foaming. At 220 °C, the gelation time coincided with the time when rapid gas liberation was occurring, this system was expected to gain sufficient gel strength to enclose the gas within the matrix, leading to stable foam formation.

Figure 2: CBA gas liberation under isothermal heating.

Figure 3: Viscosity of p-APB/PN prepolymer at different temperature

Figure 4: Diagram showing the relationship between gas liberation and viscosity change at 190 °C and 220 °C.

Foam Development

PN foam was fabricated for the first time through proper synchronization of polymerization and gas liberation. The proposed steps for the foam growth and a SEI micrograph of typical PN foam were shown in Figure 5. Upon heating, two processes occurred simultaneously: N_2 and NH_3 were released via thermal decomposition of CBA, molten polymer started to solidify by crosslinking. Gas bubbles were initiated when the gas concentration in the polymer melt exceeded the critical concentration. Bubbles were spherical when first being initiated and grew due to (i) the pressure difference between bubble and the polymer melt and (ii) the pressure difference between adjacent bubbles. Equalization of the pressure difference occurred through by growth or coalescence of smaller bubbles. Unlike typical low density polymeric foams, polygonal cell structure was not observed in any of our foam systems. Even at density as low as 0.08 g/cm^3 , the cells remained spherical with adjacent cell walls touching like those in liquid foam. It was generally accepted that bubbles remain spherical because the interfacial area and the capillary pressure are at the minimum. However, in this case, it was believed that the cells remained spherical not because of the ideal mathematical principle. The high resistance force from the increasing viscosity made further cell growth impossible.

Figure 5: The development stages of rigid PN foam. Step 1 foaming mixture, consisting of PN prepolymer and CBA, Step 2 bubble growth, Step 3 cell coalescence during cell growth and step 4 the final foam structure.

SEI micrograph showing PN foam with 2.5 wt% CBA, density of 0.15 g/cm^3 .

Effects of Temperature on Foam Development

To study the effects of temperature on foaming, CBA was fixed at 2.5 wt% and the amount of polymer used was also kept constant. When being foamed at 200 °C, foams with higher than expected density were observed, consisting of non-spherical closed cells well-separated by thick struts as shown in Figure 6(a). This morphology denotes unsuccessful foaming when the foaming temperature was too low. The insufficient amount of gas generated was unable to generate enough pressure difference to overcome the high resistance for bubble growth imposed by the high melt viscosity at low temperature.

On the other hand, the desired foam density was achieved when the temperature was increased to 280 °C, but irregular cell structure and indefinable cell shape (Figure 6(b)) was observed due to the poor control over the simultaneous reaction of polymerization and gas liberation process. Increasing the foaming temperature reduce the melt viscosity and accelerate the cell growth process simultaneously, it also increased the pressure difference and provided additional driving force for bubble growth through diffusion. However, the polymer melt with much reduced viscosity was unable to gain sufficient melt strength to stop cell coalescence during the rapid cell growth. As a result, irregular porous structure was formed.

Figure 6: PN foams foamed (a) at 200 °C and (b) at 280 °C showing unsatisfactory morphologies resulted as a result of inappropriate temperature.

Effects of CBA Content

Table 2 summarized the foam density, foaming grade, average cell diameter and cell density calculated based on Equation 5 to 8 at different CBA content with fixed amount of polymer. Foaming grade is a parameter determined by the foam density and is directly related to the concentration of CBA. The foaming grade increased with CBA wt% and reached the plateau at 2.8 wt%, after which the cell density dropped about 1 order of magnitude and the cell shape became irregular. The rate of bubble nucleation theoretically increases for higher blowing gas concentration but not the case for CBA-blown PN foam. A surplus amount of CBA (more than 3 wt %) instead of result in higher foaming grade, disturb the stability of the foaming system. Increased CBA content increased the amount dissolved gas in the polymer melt and reduced the melt viscosity through plasticizing effect and (i) reduced the melt resilience against bubble coalescence, and (ii) promoted bubble growth. It was stated that for a given volume of gas, large cells were favored to achieve energy minimization in order to ease the increased bubble pressure. At high gas concentration, bubbles grew rapidly and coalescence with bubbles in close vicinity. Merge between bubbles decreased the cell density and increased the bubble size resulting in fewer but larger cells. Excessive amount of CBA in the system caused the cell shape to be irregular and measurement is impossible.

CBA Content wt%	Density g/cm ³	Foaming Grade (%)	Average cell diameter/cm	Cell Density cell/cm ³ X 10 ⁵
0.9	0.35±0.01	54.2	0.29	0.86
1.2	0.21±0.01	65.8	0.37	1.24
1.6	0.18±0.01	68.3	0.65	4.17
2.5	0.15±0.01	70.8	0.77	3.50
2.8	0.15±0.01	70.8	0.82	3.76
3.0	0.15±0.02	70.8	1.05	0.41
3.5	0.15±0.02	70.8	-*	-*

* Measurement was impossible due to the indefinable cell morphology.

Table 1: Relationship of CBA content in wt% to average cell diameter and cell density.

Thermal Stabilities of PN Foams

Table 2 summarized the excellent thermal oxidative parameters of PN foam. Char yield of the 0.2 g/cm³ foams were found to be 82.3 and 68.5 wt% in N₂ and air respectively. The values were comparable to its void free samples and unattainable by most thermoset foams. Even at density as low as 0.08 g/cm³, the char yield at 800 °C in N₂ was maintained at 63.5%. The high thermal stability was attributed by the high crosslinking density and the thermally stable structures formed during crosslinking.

Density	Onset Degradation °C (5 wt% Loss)		Char Yield at 600 °C (wt %)		Char Yield at 800 °C (wt %)	
	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air
0.08	496	483	75.3	62.3	62.9	13.5
0.12	478	465	77.1	70.5	63.9	13.6
0.15	490	481	78.9	73.6	65.6	14.6
0.20	511	500	82.3	77.7	68.2	17.8

Table 2: Thermal oxidative parameters of PN foams obtained by TGA.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this paper presents for the first time, the development of PN based foam through a synchronized gelation-gas liberation process. The study highlighted the importance of the establishment of a balanced relationship between polymer gelation and CBA gas liberation for foam fabrication. The final foam morphologies were affected by the CBA content and the foaming temperature. Excessive CBA increased the cell size and the cell size distribution due to plasticizing effect on the polymer melt. Increased foaming temperature would accelerate cell growth through reducing the polymer melt strength. The properly cured RPh foams showed superior thermal properties which were unattainable by other reported thermoset foams.

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